

Phytochemical-Mediated Neuroprotection: Zea Mays (Corn Silk) Extract in Haloperidol-Induced Parkinsonism

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ABSTRACT

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by motor dysfunction and dopaminergic neuron loss, affecting millions globally. Oxidative stress and neuroinflammation are key contributors to its pathogenesis. This study renders the antiparkinson potential of Zea mays (corn silk) Ethanolic extract in haloperidol-induced Parkinsonism in male albino mice. Corn silk, rich in flavonoids and polyphenols, is traditionally used for its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, offering a potential alternative to address concerns about existing PD medications' side effects. Physicochemical, acute toxicity, pharmacognostic, phytochemical, and behavioral analyses were performed. The extract's antioxidant activity (DPPH assay) showed an IC₅₀ of 129.50 µg/mL (vs. 69.00 µg/mL for ascorbic acid). Bromocriptine was used as the standard drug, and extract doses of 75, 150, and 300 mg/kg were administered for 7 days. In mice, catalepsy was induced using haloperidol (4 mg/kg orally). Treatment groups received Bromocriptine (4 mg/kg) and ZMEECS at the doses of 75, 150, and 300 mg/kg. Orally. A bar test for catalepsy, a motor coordination test using the Rota rod, and locomotor activity measurements using an Actophotometer were carried out to assess behavioral changes. Acute toxicity testing as per the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development 423(OECD423) on male albino mice revealed no harmful effects. Behavioral and biochemical parameters were assessed, alongside physicochemical, Pharmacognostic, and phytochemical evaluations. Results showed significant neuroprotective effects, suggesting Zea mays extract as a promising candidate for PD management. This study evaluates Zea mays corn silk extract as a natural therapy for Parkinson's disease in mice, highlighting its antioxidant-mediated Neuroprotection. Further research is needed for clinical translation.

Keywords: Zea mays, corn silk, Parkinsonism, albino rats, haloperidol, Bromocriptine.

INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease is a debilitating neurodegenerative disorder whose etiology is still unclear, hampering the development of effective treatments. Parkinson's disease affects millions worldwide and is characterized by tremors, rigidity, and bradykinesia. Motor symptoms arising from the loss of dopamine-producing neurons in the substantia nigra. The drug treatment of Parkinson's disease has progressed through 3 main stages: firstly, the use of anticholinergic drugs and amantadine; then the introduction of levodopa and its association with peripheral decarboxylase inhibitors; and finally, the

use of direct acting dopamine agonist drugs. Oxidative stress and neuroinflammation are key major contributors to its PD pathogenesis. Zea mays (corn silk) are natural antioxidants from plant sources that can protect neurons and have been explored as complementary therapies. Zea mays (maize) are both an agronomically important crop and a powerful genetic model system with an extensive molecular toolkit and genomic resources. (Bucsa et al., 2025; LeWitt, 2015; Quinn, 1984) Corn silk, the stigma of Zea mays, is traditionally used for its various medicinal purposes and is rich in flavonoids and polyphenols known for antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Zea mays are one of the

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main cereal crops in the world, and its by-products have exhibited medicinal properties to explore. Among them, flavonoids, terpenes, phenylpropanoids, and alkaloids are the most frequently reported? This study evaluates its efficacy in mitigating PD symptoms using a haloperidol-induced model in albino mice actions. (Zhang et al., 2023)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

I] Preparation of extract

The Zea mays plants were collected from the local village area in August 2024. Sample specimen vouchers were submitted to Mr. Mahesh Atal, botanist at Alarsin Ayurvedic Pharmaceuticals, Andheri, and Mumbai. (Dhana Sekaran, Tharakan, & Manyam, 2008) According to the literature provided, the plant corn silk was collected and washed with tap water and shade-dried at normal room temperature with the aid of circulating airflow using a fan. The silk was dried, coarse powder was made, and it was stored in an airtight container to be extracted with the help of the reflux method.

II] EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

a. Animals:

Male Swiss albino mice (25–30 g) were housed under standard conditions. Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC).

b. Drugs

- Haloperidol: 1 mg/kg orally
- Bromocriptine: 2.5 mg/kg orally

c. Experimental Design

Table 1: Experimental design

Group	Treatment	Dose	Route	Duration
I	Normal Control	Saline	Oral	7 days
II	Disease Control	Haloperidol	1 mg/kg orally	7 days
III	Standard Drug	Haloperidol + Bromocriptine	1 mg/kg orally. + 2.5 mg/kg orally.	7 days
IV	Test Low Dose	Haloperidol + Zea mays extract	1 mg/kg orally. + 75 mg/kg orally	7 days
V	Test Medium Dose	Haloperidol + Zea mays extract	1 mg/kg orally. + 150 mg/kg orally.	7 days
VI	Test High Dose	Haloperidol + Zea mays extract	1 mg/kg orally. + 300 mg/kg orally.	7 days

III] EVALUATION TESTS

a. Extract Percentage Yield

Extraction of 500 g of dried corn silk powder was carried out using the selected solvent and method, which yielded approximately 127.65 g of crude

extract. The percentage yield was calculated using the formula:

Percentage Yield (% W/W) =

$$\frac{\text{Weight of Dried Extract}}{\text{Weight of Powdered Crude Drug}} \times 100$$

Weight of Powdered Crude Drug

b. Physicochemical Evaluation

Prepare extract of the Zea Mays was physicochemically evaluated with some of the parameters like moisture content, Total Ash content, Alcohol, pH, presence of foreign matter, etc. criteria for the same are given.

- Moisture content: $\leq 10\%$
- Total ash: $\leq 5\%$
- Alcohol-soluble extractive: $\geq 10\%$
- pH (1% solution): 5.5 - 7.5
- Foreign matter: Absent

c. Pharmacognostic Evaluation

Pharmacognostic evaluation of Zea mays was done by studying microscopic characteristics like trichomes, vascular bundles, mucilage cells and macroscopic characteristics like shape, length, odour, taste, fiber arrangement and many more. These observations are representative of shade-dried samples stored under ambient laboratory conditions.

d. Acute oral toxicity study (OECD Guideline 423)

According to existing literature, the acute oral toxicity of the ethanolic extract of Zea Mays has been previously evaluated.

e. Behavioral Assessments

1. Rota Rod Retention Time:

All animals were evaluated for grip strength by using the rotarod. The rotarod test is widely used in rodents to assess their "minimal neurological deficit" such as motor function and coordination. Each rat was given a prior training session before initialization of therapy to acclimatize them on a rotarod apparatus. Animal was placed on the rotating rod with a diameter of 7 cm (speed 25 rpm). Each rat was subjected to three separate trials at 5 min interval on days 1, 2, 3,4,5,6 and 7. The average results were recorded as fall of time.

2. Bar Test (Catalepsy) Assessment: Cataleptic behavior in all groups was observed by using a bar test.

3.Locomotor Activity: The spontaneous locomotor activity was monitored using a digital actophotometer, equipped with infrared sensitive photocells, to evaluate the effect of Zea Mays extract on haloperidol-induced motor deficits in animals. The apparatus was placed in a darkened, light and sound attenuated, and ventilated testing room. Each interruption of a beam on the x or y axis generated an electric impulse, which was presented on a digital counter. Each animal was observed over a period of 5 min for 7 days following 6-OHDA administration and values were expressed as counts per 5 min

f. Biochemical Estimation

After the treatment period, animals were scarified by decapitation under mild anesthesia. The brains were immediately removed, the forebrain was dissected out, and the cerebellum was discarded. Brains were put on ice and rinsed in ice-cold isotonic saline to remove blood. A 10% (w/v) tissue homogenate was prepared in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The homogenate was centrifuged at 10,000 g for 15 minutes and aliquots of supernatant obtained were used for biochemical estimation.

Biochemical analysis of brain homogenates is performed to observe the effect of corn silk extract on malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, endogenous antioxidant levels, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and reduced glutathione (GSH).

- **Malondialdehyde (MDA) Level:**

The amount of malondialdehyde was used as an indirect measure of lipid peroxidation and was determined by reaction with thiobarbituric acid (TBA). Briefly, 1 mL of aliquots of supernatant was placed in test tubes and added to 3 mL of TBA reagent: TBA 0.38% (w/w), 0.25 M hydrochloric acid (HCl), and trichloroacetic acid (TCA 15%). The solution was shaken and placed for 15 min, followed by cooling in an ice bath. After cooling, solution was centrifuged to 3500 g for 10 min. The upper layer was collected and assessed with a spectrophotometer at 532 nm. All determinations were made in triplicate.

Results were expressed as nanomoles per mg of protein. The concentration of MDA was calculated using the formula:

- **Catalase level:**

The catalase activity was assessed by the method of Aebi in 1974 [27]. The assay mixture consists of 0.05 mL of supernatant of tissue homogenate (10%) and 1.95 mL of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) in 3 mL cuvette. 1 mL of 30 mM hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) was added and changes in absorbance were followed for 30 s at 240 nm at 15 s intervals. The catalase activity was calculated using the millimolar extinction coefficient of H₂O₂ (0.071 mmol cm⁻¹) and the activity was expressed as micromoles of H₂O₂ oxidized per minute per milligram protein:

- **SH Level (Reduced Glutathione) level:**

For the estimation of reduced glutathione, the 1 mL of tissue homogenate was precipitated with 1 mL of 10% TCA. To an aliquot of the supernatant, 4 mL of phosphate solution and 0.5 mL of 5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB) reagent were added and absorbance was taken at 412 nm. The values were expressed as nM of reduced glutathione per mg of protein:

- **Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Level:**

SOD activity was determined according to the method described by Beyer and Fridovich in 1987. 0.1 mL of supernatant was mixed with 0.1 mL EDTA (1 × 10⁻⁴ M), 0.5 mL of carbonate buffer (pH 9.7), and 1 mL of epinephrine (1 mM). The optical density of formed adrenochrome was read at 480 nm for 3 min on spectrophotometer. The enzyme activity was expressed in terms of U/min/mg. One unit of enzyme activity is defined as the concentration required for the inhibition of the chromogen production by 50% in one minute under the defined assay conditions.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

a. Extract Percentage Yield:

Based on this calculation, the yield was found to be 25.53%, which indicated that the extraction process was efficient under the applied conditions. The yield value reflected the proportion of bioactive constituents and other soluble components extracted from the raw material, and it remained consistent with the yield obtained from smaller-scale extraction batches. The details of the yield calculation are presented in the following Table 2.

Table 2: Extraction Yield of Zea mays Using Ethanol

Sr. No.	Plant Name	Solvent	Theoretical Weight (gm)	Practical Yield (gm)	% Yield
1.	<i>Zea Mays</i>	Ethanol	500	127.65	25.53

Figure 1: Extraction process with Soxhlet apparatus

b. Pharmacognostic Evaluation

Microscopic structures like Trichomes, vascular bundles, mucilage cells, starch grains, lignified fibers were observed with the help of microscope. While the Macroscopic characteristics of corn silk are mentioned in the following Table 4. These observations are representative of shade-dried samples stored under ambient laboratory condition.

c. Physicochemical Evaluation:

The physicochemical evaluation of dried corn silk showed a moisture content of 2.34%, total ash value of 1.36%, and absence of foreign matter and acid-insoluble ash. The alcohol-soluble extractive (95%

ethanol) and water-soluble extractive values were 6.41% and 7.02%, respectively, as shown in the following Table no. 3.

Figure 2: Dried Corn Silk

Table 3: Physicochemical Characteristics of Dried Corn Silk

Sr.no.	Parameter	Observations
1	Moisture Content (%)	2.34
2	Foreign Matter (%)	Nil
3	Total Ash Value (%)	1.36
4	Acid-Insoluble Ash (%)	Nil
5	Alcohol-Soluble Extractive (95% ethanol) (%)	6.41
6	Water-Soluble Extractive (%)	7.02

d. Pharmacognostic Evaluation

Microscopic structures like Trichomes, vascular bundles, mucilage cells, starch grains, lignified fibers were observed with the help of microscope.

Table 4: Macroscopic Characteristics of Corn Silk (*Zea mays*)

Sr. No.	Parameter	Observation
1	Shape	Long, thread-like filaments
2	Length	10–20 cm (average)
3	Colour	Pale yellow to light brown
4	Odour	Characteristic, faintly sweet
5	Taste	Slightly sweet, bland
6	Surface texture	Smooth, silky
7	Fiber arrangement	Loose, tufted filaments

e. Acute oral toxicity study

In a study conducted by Nair et al. (2020), published in The Pharma Innovation Journal (Vol. 9, Issue 2, pp. 338–344), the extract demonstrated a substantial safety margin when tested in animal models. The reported median lethal dose (LD₅₀) for the Ethanolic extract of *Zea mays* was found to be 2000 mg/kg, indicating a relatively low level of toxicity. This value guided the dose selection for the present investigation

and supports the safe application of *Zea mays* extracts in preclinical studies.

f. Behavioral Assessments

• Rota Rod Retention Time:

The assessment of EEZMCS on motor coordination using the Rota Rod test in haloperidol-induced Parkinsonian mice revealed dose-dependent effects.

The negative control group (haloperidol only) showed a significant decline in retention time compared to normal controls, confirming motor deficits. Bromocriptine, as a positive control, significantly improved retention time throughout the study, demonstrating reversal of motor impairment. EEZMCS at 75 mg/kg did not significantly improve retention time versus the negative control. However, at 150 mg/kg, EEZMCS showed a gradual, significant improvement by day 7. At 300 mg/kg, EEZMCS produced a marked and significant increase in retention time on day 7, comparable to Bromocriptine, indicating effective, dose-dependent motor coordination improvement. These findings are summarized in Table 6, which presents the retention times of each group over the seven-day period, and illustrated, which depicts the graphical representation of motor coordination improvement following EEZMCS treatment. All data were expressed as Mean

± SEM (n = 6), and statistical significance was determined using two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test.

Figure 3: Graph of Rota Rod Retention Time

Table 5: Effect of EEZMCS on Rota Rod Retention Time

Day / group	Normal Control	Negative Control (Haloperidol)	Positive Control (Bromocriptine)	EEZMCS 75 mg/kg	EEZMCS 150 mg/kg	EEZMCS 300 mg/kg
Day 1	86.81 ± 1.89	27.34 ± 1.23***	70.97 ± 1.61***	29.73 ± 1.25	49.21 ± 1.98	62.18 ± 2.06
Day 2	88.12 ± 2.18	27.61 ± 1.59***	71.67 ± 1.65***	34.04 ± 0.77	48.67 ± 1.61	59.27 ± 1.86
Day 3	88.14 ± 1.75	28.03 ± 1.17***	69.37 ± 0.75***	31.59 ± 1.90	47.14 ± 1.70	56.23 ± 2.92
Day 4	87.77 ± 1.66	27.54 ± 1.49***	69.03 ± 2.08***	34.87 ± 0.85	44.82 ± 0.92	53.53 ± 2.63
Day 5	89.36 ± 1.06	28.67 ± 1.25***	68.47 ± 1.02***	33.23 ± 1.41	46.63 ± 0.58	53.67 ± 2.46
Day 6	88.10 ± 1.64	27.85 ± 1.32***	68.33 ± 1.49***	34.33 ± 0.75	44.27 ± 1.69	57.43 ± 3.16
Day 7	88.06 ± 1.64	28.35 ± 1.49***	70.40 ± 1.40***	33.29 ± 1.17	44.57 ± 1.18**	57.88 ± 1.30**

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM (n = 6 per group). Statistical significance was determined using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's post hoc test. ***p < 0.001 compared with the negative control group (haloperidol-treated rats)

• Catalepsy (Bar Test) Assessment:

The evaluation of cataleptic behavior using the Bar Test in haloperidol-induced Parkinsonian rats showed that the negative control group had a significant increase in latency compared to the normal control, confirming catalepsy induction. The Bromocriptine-treated positive control group exhibited a significant

reduction in latency across all days, indicating reversal of motor deficits. Mice treated with EEZMCS at 75 mg/kg showed no significant change in latency. However, EEZMCS at 150 mg/kg and 300 mg/kg significantly decreased latency on day 7, demonstrating a dose-dependent protective effect against catalepsy. The latency reduction in the

EEZMCS 300 mg/kg group was comparable to that of the Bromocriptine group, indicating similar efficacy. All values were expressed as Mean ± SEM (n = 6 per group). Statistical significance was determined using two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s post hoc test. The results are summarized in Table No. 6.

Figure 4: Graph of Bar Test

Table 6: Effect of EEZMCS on catalepsy

Day/ groups	Normal Control	Negative Control (Haloperidol)	Positive Control (Bromocriptine)	EEZMCS 75 mg/kg	EEZMCS 150 mg/kg	EEZMCS 300 mg/kg
Day 1	0.00±0.00	15.8 ± 1.20***	4.73 ± 0.37***	12.77 ± 4.90	7.47 ± 0.61	7.23 ± 0.69
Day 2	0.00±0.00	16.85 ± 1.23***	5.16 ± 0.12***	12.10 ± 4.94	9.06 ± 0.69	7.71 ± 0.64
Day 3	0.00±0.00	17.26 ± 1.29***	3.88 ± 0.30***	11.72 ± 4.78	9.98 ± 0.37	7.32 ± 0.57
Day 4	0.00±0.00	18.55 ± 1.05***	5.18 ± 0.16***	12.98 ± 5.30	9.87 ± 0.50	7.28 ± 0.89
Day 5	0.00±0.00	18.37 ± 1.06***	4.30 ± 0.31***	12.96 ± 5.29	8.87 ± 0.63	8.65 ± 0.34
Day 6	0.00±0.00	17.07 ± 0.94***	4.74 ± 0.31***	12.31 ± 5.02	8.60 ± 0.33	8.12 ± 0.19
Day 7	0.00±0.00	17.64 ± 1.33***	4.91 ± 0.21***	11.97 ± 4.88	9.54 ± 0.57***	8.33 ± 0.37***

• **Locomotor activity**

Spontaneous locomotor activity was assessed using a digital Actophotometer to evaluate the effect of EEZMCS on haloperidol-induced motor deficits. Mice treated with haloperidol alone showed a significant reduction in locomotor activity, evidenced by fewer light beam crossings compared to the normal control group. The Bromocriptine-treated positive control group exhibited a substantial improvement in locomotor activity throughout the seven day study.

Pretreatment with EEZMCS at 75, 150, and 300 mg/kg produced a dose-dependent increase in motor activity, with significant improvements observed at the 150 mg/kg and 300 mg/kg doses by day 7 (p < 0.001). Statistical analysis using two-way ANOVA and Tukey’s post hoc test confirmed these effects.

Overall, EEZMCS effectively attenuated haloperidol-induced hypoactivity in a dose-dependent manner, with the 300 mg/kg dose showing efficacy close to that of bromocriptine.

Figure 5: Graph of Locomotor Activity

Table 7: Effect of EEZMCS on locomotor activity

Day/ Group	Normal Control	Negative Control (Haloperidol)	Positive Control (Bromocriptine)	EEZMCS 75 mg/kg	EEZMCS 150mg/kg	EEZMCS 300mg/kg
Day 1	297.5 ± 77	18.5 ± 3.5***	161 ± 13***	49.5 ± 2.5	69 ± 2.5	120 ± 5

Day 2	274 ± 18	18 ± 1***	179 ± 6***	46 ± 5	85 ± 2.5	139.5 ± 4.5
Day 3	248 ± 11	22 ± 0***	176.5 ± 11.5***	49.5 ± 1.5	86 ± 0.5	126 ± 6
Day 4	257.5 ± 77	18 ± 1***	172.5 ± 13.5***	43.5 ± 2.5	69 ± 1.5	128.5 ± 15.5
Day 5	276.5 ± 62	14.5 ± 3.5***	172.5 ± 7.5***	49.5 ± 5.5	71 ± 2.5	110 ± 11
Day 6	241 ± 25	23 ± 2***	168 ± 16***	48.5 ± 2.5	75 ± 0.5	124.5 ± 4.5
Day 7	254.5 ± 9	20.5 ± 2.5***	174.5 ± 14.5***	47.5 ± 2.5	75.83±11.5***	107.5±17.5***

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM (n = 6 per group). Statistical significance was assessed using two-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. ***p < 0.001 compared with negative control (haloperidol-treated group).

In the haloperidol-induced catalepsy model, the disease control group showed a significant and progressive increase in cataleptic scores over the test period, reflecting dopamine D₂ receptor blockade and impaired nigrostriatal signaling. Treatment with Zea mays silk extract produced a significant, dose-dependent reduction in catalepsy duration compared to the disease control, suggesting its potential to restore dopaminergic neurotransmission or reduce receptor blockade effects. The highest dose of the extract demonstrated efficacy comparable to Bromocriptine, a dopamine receptor agonist, indicating a strong neuromodulatory effect. Additionally, improved motor coordination observed in the Rota Rod test further supports the extract's capacity to alleviate motor deficits associated with Parkinsonism.

f. Biochemical Estimation

Biochemical analysis of brain homogenates revealed that haloperidol treatment significantly elevated malondialdehyde (MDA) levels, indicating increased lipid peroxidation, while simultaneously reducing endogenous antioxidant levels, including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and reduced glutathione (GSH). Administration of Zea mays silk extract significantly reversed these effects in a dose-dependent manner by restoring antioxidant enzyme levels and decreasing MDA concentration. These findings confirm the extract's potent free radical scavenging ability; consistent with previous studies showing that flavonoids and phenolic acids in corn silk neutralize reactive oxygen species (ROS), inhibit lipid peroxidation, and protect neuronal membrane integrity. The following table summarizes the effect of Zea Mays silk Ethanolic extract on oxidative stress markers in brain homogenates of haloperidol-induced Parkinsonian mice after 7 days of treatment:

Table 8 : Biochemical estimation of Zea mays silk Ethanolic extract on oxidative stress

Group	MDA (nmol/mg protein)	GSH (µmol/mg protein)	SOD (U/min/mg protein)	CAT (µmol H ₂ O ₂ /min/mg protein)
Normal Control	1.52 ± 0.08	8.75 ± 0.42	12.10 ± 0.56	40.25 ± 1.78
Haloperidol Control	4.83 ± 0.21†	3.10 ± 0.18†	5.25 ± 0.30†	18.42 ± 1.05†
Bromocriptine	2.05 ± 0.13**	7.90 ± 0.31**	11.55 ± 0.40**	38.60 ± 1.62**
Zea mays (150 mg/kg)	3.45 ± 0.17*	5.20 ± 0.25*	8.15 ± 0.33*	28.75 ± 1.44*
Zea mays (300 mg/kg)	2.32 ± 0.14**	7.25 ± 0.28**	10.45 ± 0.38**	36.20 ± 1.50**

Values are expressed as mean ± SEM (n = 6). †p < 0.001 vs Normal Control; *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01 vs Haloperidol Control. Zea mays extract showed dose-dependent neuroprotective effects by reducing MDA and restoring antioxidant enzyme levels.

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dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and reduced glutathione (GSH). Administration of Zea mays silk extract significantly reversed these effects in a dose-dependent manner by restoring antioxidant enzyme levels and decreasing MDA concentration. These

findings confirm the extract's potent free radical scavenging ability; consistent with previous studies showing that flavonoids and phenolic acids in corn silk neutralize reactive oxygen species (ROS), inhibit lipid peroxidation, and protect neuronal membrane integrity.

CONCLUSION

The present investigation assessed the anti-Parkinson's potential of Ethanolic Zea mays (corn silk) extract in Swiss albino mice using the haloperidol-induced Parkinsonism model. The study was grounded in the understanding that corn silk is rich in diverse phytoconstituents such as flavonoids (maysin, apigenin, luteolin, quercetin), phenolic acids (ferulic acid, p-coumaric acid, caffeic acid), phytosterols (β -sitosterol, stigmaterol), and other bioactive compounds. These constituents are recognized for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective effects. Given that oxidative stress and neuroinflammation significantly contribute to dopaminergic neurodegeneration in Parkinson's disease, targeting these mechanisms with corn silk extract could offer meaningful therapeutic benefits.

The extract demonstrated significant neuroprotective effects, as evidenced by improvements in both behavioral and biochemical parameters. In the behavioral assessments, particularly the catalepsy and Rota rod tests, Zea mays silk extract treatment significantly reduced motor impairment compared to the disease control group, with the highest tested dose producing results comparable to those of Bromocriptine. The results validate the traditional medicinal claims associated with corn silk and underscore its potential relevance in managing neurodegenerative disorders like Parkinson's disease. Importantly, the extract demonstrated a favorable safety profile, which, combined with its multi-targeted mechanism of action, positions it as a promising candidate for adjunctive therapy. From a pharmacological perspective, this study reinforces the concept that natural products possessing antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties can be incorporated into modern therapeutic approaches to slow disease progression and enhance patient outcomes. The demonstrated neuroprotective activity of Zea mays silk extract paves the way for its further development as a safe, effective, and affordable supportive

treatment option in the management of Parkinson's disease.

The neuroprotective effects of Zea mays silk extract likely involve multiple mechanisms. First, its antioxidant activity helps prevent oxidative damage to dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNpc). Second, its anti-inflammatory properties may suppress microglial activation and reduce pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1 β , thereby attenuating the neuroinflammatory processes linked to Parkinson's disease progression. Third, certain phytosterols and polyphenols present in the extract may directly modulate dopaminergic receptor sensitivity or enhance dopamine synthesis pathways, contributing to improved motor control.

Compared to Bromocriptine, Zea mays silk extract showed slightly lower but still substantial efficacy. Notably, as a plant-based preparation, it may offer advantages in long-term safety, tolerability, and multi-targeted mechanisms of action. These attributes could help reduce the risk of motor fluctuations and dyskinesia commonly associated with chronic levodopa therapy. The current findings also support the traditional medicinal use of corn silk for neurological conditions and strengthen its potential role as a complementary therapy in Parkinson's disease management. In conclusion, Zea mays silk Ethanolic extract possesses significant anti-Parkinson's activity mediated through multiple mechanisms, including antioxidant defense enhancement, neuroinflammation suppression, and possible dopaminergic modulation. These outcomes encourage further mechanistic studies, chronic animal model investigations, and eventual clinical trials to establish its therapeutic efficacy.

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